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Challenges of social safety nets in Indonesia

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Abstract

Social safety nets (SSNt) is a form of government involvement in providing assistance to need live of the poor and vulnerable for increase the quality of life people. This study is an introduction that discusses the concept and program of SSNt among fishermen in South Sulawesi Province. How SSNt interests and challenges in improving people's quality of life.

Keywords: Social Safety Nets (SSNt), Quality of Life, Poor Fishermen.

Introduction

The Social Safety Net (SSNt) Program is aimed at improving the quality of life of people primarily in basic needs such as food, access to education, access to health and housing. Therefore, the SSNt program must be well-organized and implemented in order to succeed in reducing poverty (Ravallion, 2003). Individuals or communities are said to be of inferiority if basic needs are not met based on the theory of human development needs or the quality of life stage (Sirgy, 1986).

According to Ravallion (2003) JPS not only reduces short-term poverty, but theory and some statistical evidence indicates a positive influence on economic growth and community welfare by helping the create skilled workers. Many studies have found that SSNt helps improve the quality of life of people (Hadi et al., 2004; Ravallion, 2003; Shahnewaz and Tareq, 2013; Pradhan et al., 2013; Hirano and Otsubo, 2014). SSNt program has an important role in building economic growth, social life and environment. In the past two decades, social assistance has given direct impact to the poor with an increase in income and economic growth (Hirano and Otsubo, 2014).

Therefore, economic stimulation and social services through various forms of SSNt need to be run to improve the quality of life of the community. In Indonesia, various SSNt programs have been implemented starting from the economic crisis in mid 1997 to the present with the budget tending to increase every year, but the fluctuating poverty number. The latest data from the Indonesian Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) in 2014 stated that the number of Indonesian poverty increased to 28.28 million compared to the year 2013, which is 28.06 million. The same thing happened in South Sulawesi from 806 thousand

in 2012 to 864 thousand in 2014. Although the level of education, the number of school participation, income, life expectancy and the average length of school increases every year, but in reality there are many low community life in Makassar City, South Sulawesi, especially fishermen (Asang, 2012). Thus, the implementation of the SSNt program is also a lot of challenges such as data collection/updating, administrative, financial, information, infrastructure, geographic, cultural and community capacity.

The quality of life of fishermen is generally still backward compared to other professions such as farmers, laborers, informal workers and generally living outside the city (Isaac, 1990; Kusnadi, 2001; Suharto, 2010). Therefore, to encourage the quality of life of the fishermen, the government established a program of Improving the Life of Fishermen (PKN) based on Presidential Decree number 10, Year 2011 on Coordination Team for Improvement and Expansion of Pro-People's Program with the chairman of the Minister of Marine and Fisheries with 12 members of the Ministry. PKN program that is; (i) building low-cost housing; (ii) skills training; (iii) micro, small and community business credit schemes; (iv) construction of diesel fuel; (v) the construction of cold storage; (vi) cheap public transportation; (vii) school facilities and health services, and (viii) public bank facilities. This program is run because according to the Minister of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Sharif C Sutardjo there are 7.8 million people or 25% of the poor (Lensa Indonesia, 2012) while South Sulawesi province the fourth largest number of poor fishermen families in Indonesia based on data Ministry of Marine and Fisheries year 2011.

The issue of quality of life is a major issue especially in East Indonesia Region (KIT) such as Sulawesi Island, Kalimantan, Nusa Tenggara, Maluku and Papua because it has minimal development facilities compared to West Indonesia Region such as access to education, health, infrastructure and and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of 2004-2008 is just under 20% compared to West Indonesia Region (KIB) which consists of Java Island, Sumatera and Bali exceeding 80% (Harefa, 2010), and supported by Kuncoro (2004) that there are the quality of life gap between KIB and KIT even decline in KIT. These represents a developmental challenge to the overall quality of life in Indonesia (Marsuki, 2010).

Quality of life can be measured through the Human Development Index (HDI), literacy rate, the average length of school, life expectancy and purchasing power parity (UNDP, 2013), or World Health Organization (WHO) measurement through individual perception such as physical health, psychology, social relations, freedom and the environment (Marvin, 1997). Then the Seterusnya Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) by 2015; to eradicate extreme poverty and hunger, universal primary education, to promote gender equality and empower women, to reduce child mortality, to improve maternal health, to combat HIV/AIDS, mmalaria, and other diseases, to ensure environment sustainability and to develop a global partnership for development (World Bank, 2015). According to Harun and Idris (2012) to measure quality of life of the indigenous people in Malaysia with the quality of life of the Index indigenous weighted (IKHOAw) e.g. index of water supply, index of electric supply, the house is strong and comfortable, index of sanitation, index of engine, ability to live societal and free of disease. So do other researchers such as Baris and Osman (2003), Dalia and Juozas (2007), Azahan et al. (2008), Dalia and Algirdas (2009), Lyndon et al. (2011), Zhanna (2014) and Olivas et al. (2014) have different concepts, measurements and quality of life responses.

What is the Social Safety Net (SSNt), Quality of Life and SSNt Program Challenges to Improve the Quality of Life Community?

A. Social Safety Net (SSNt)

According to World Bank (2014) Social Safety Nets (SSNt) are non-contributory transfers designed to provide regular and predictable support to targeted poor and vulnerable. These are also referred to as “social assistance” or social transfers.” By combining different “modalities” and “classes” of transfer, a family of five have been examined (i) conditional cash transfers, (ii) unconditional cash transfers, (iii) conditional in-kind transfers, (iv) unconditional in-kind transfers), and (v) public works. SSNt are a component of wider social protection system, such as Diagram 1.

Diagram 1. SSNt are a component of Social Protection Systems (World Bank, 2014).

Meanwhile the Asian Development Bank (ADB), SSNt is a policy group devised to reduce poverty and range through improving people's lives, protecting them from disasters and loss of income. ADB consists of five elements: (i) the labor market, (ii) social insurance, (iii) social assistance, (iv) micro schemes for the protection of local communities, and (v) child protection (Zhang et al., 2010).

SSNt types in developed countries such as Europe, USA, Japan and Australia are using cash aid such as parental allowance, orphan and single father or mother, while countries are developing more for non-financial assistance such as children's education and health care (Tabor, 2002) and for less-developing countries using more public works such as opening jobs for unemployment or labor incentives such as building or improvement of public facilities and community infrastructure (Smith and Subbarao, 2013, World Bank, 2014).

Furthermore, according to Suharto (2006), the SSNt program encompasses five types; (i) market policies/employment opportunities (ii) social assistance to orphans, single mothers, elderly, disabled, homeless, beggars, sex workers, HIV/AIDS patients, backward

indigenous communities, street children, child laborers, retired, elderly; (iii) social insurance such as health insurance, labor, accident, disability, elderly pension, pension, and death; (iv) community-based schemes to protect against risks such as arisan groups, payroll, self-funded death funds, and patrol posts; (v) child neglect, child labor, child abuse and street child.

Meanwhile Pradhan et al. (2013) divides SSNt into three public policy; (i) social that is the various activities of individuals, families, communities and organizations for the quality of physics, protection, education, health, housing and employment, (ii) the economy such as business, finance, fiscal, taxes, food and commerce, (iii), other policies that are more resilient to aspects of life such as access to schools, housing, energy sources, assets, income, pensions, security, and others. According to the Prime Minister of Malaysia (Datuk Seri Ahmad Badawi) that SSNt includes services such as virtue, treatment, unemployment assistance, protection centers and subsidies to help the poor (Bernama, 2009).

B. Social Safety Nets (SSNt) Goals

Social security in Indonesia is based on the Constitution of the 1945 article 28h verse 3 that : "Every person shall have the right to social security in order to develop oneself fully as a dignified human being. The next article 34 verse 2 that : "The state shall develop a sytem of social security for all of the people and shall empower inadequate and underprivileged in society in accordance with human dignity" (UUD, 1945: 54). The main goal of the social safety net (JPS) is to reduce poverty and injustice, help future investments, help targets in managing multiple risks and assist governments in developing economic reforms to improve people's well-being (Grosh et al., 2008; Devereus, 2002; Smith dan Subbarao, 2003; Roosgandha dan Darwis, 2003; Sumarto et al., 2005; Pradhan et al., 2013; Shahnewaz dan Tareq, 2013; Rozita dan Ummu, 2014). Furthermore, the Prime Minister of Malaysia (Datuk Seri Ahmad Badawi) stated that JPS aims for the welfare of the people by providing various assistance and easing the burden of society, especially the low income and the less fortunate in order to benefit from the JPS program (Bernama, 2009).

C. Quality of life

There are different concepts and measurements of quality of life. Therefore, no experts agree on the concept of quality of life comprehensively. According to Ventegodt et al. (2003) that the integrative of the quality of life theory may be viewed objectively and subjectively. Objectively such as the needs of biology, the fulfillment of basic needs, self potential can be developed follow the cultural norms in which individuals live. While subjective is the perception of the meaning of life, happiness, satisfaction and well-being. Thus, the quality of life gives the difference of concept and measurement objectively and subjectively.

Study Olivas et al. (2014) in Jalisco, Mexico considers the social aspect of the family being primary in the quality of life of small fishermen (Olivas et al., 2014), with Ismail's (2007) study in Mandar Sulawesi Barat that social and cultural relations are a priority for fishermen. Furthermore, the study of Dalia and Algirdas (2009) in Lithuania found security and income to be primary in quality of life and then, Dalia and Juozas (2007), and Lepage (2009) stated that physical and material health is a key aspect in measuring quality of life compared to other aspects. Then according to Azahan et al. (2008) in urban areas that

environmental progress can be a measure of people's quality of life, but it does not mean that their quality of life is also good because it depends on people's perceptions of their environmental acceptance. Measurements of quality of life through human development index (HDI) such as Baris and Osman's (2003) study in the European Union used two aspects: health such as infant/maternal mortality, life expectancy, health fund, hospital room number per thousand souls as a measurement of life healthy, education (primary and secondary school enrollment rates, average literacy and access to knowledge).

C. Social Safety Net (SSNt): Interest and Challenge

Based on the theory and statistical evidence that the Social Safety Net (SSNt) can reduce poverty and improving economic growth and income (Ravallion, 2003; Hirano and Otsubo, 2014). The SSNt program is essential for countries that have poor communities. Financial capacity, administration and information, and infrastructure factors determine the success of the SSNt program (Smith and Subbarao, 2003; Raduan et al., 2007; Dwicaksono et al., 2012; Muchlisin et al., 2013; Shaladdin et al., 2010).

According to Neubourg (2002) that SSNt beneficiaries generally cannot vote or comment on administrative procedures, so the government has a monopoly power. Thus, Lola et al. (2014) that the unsuccessful SSNt program is due; (i) improperly used approaches and misdirected delivery, (ii) multi-complex issues, approaches should not be one aspect, but many aspects are integrated, consistent, and sustainable and involve the poor to find the cause of poverty and together problem solving. Therefore, according to Tabor (2002) not all regions or countries can succeed in SSNt program because it is influenced by category, geographical and cultural society.

C.1. The Interest of SSNt among the fisherman communities

The introduction of studies in South Sulawesi province with poor people in 2013 than 800 thousand people and generally plural communities 696,910 people and urban communities 160,530 people (BPS, 2014). The number of poor people generally works as farmers, fishermen, laborers and street vendors or informal workers. Based on data from the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries in 2011, there were 29,902 families or 149,510 poor fishermen in the province of South Sulawesi and including the province of 4 poor fishermen after East Java (54,824), Central Java (49,880) and North Sumatra (45,723) families.

Therefore, the importance of the social protection system, especially the social safety net (JPS) program for the poor and the range, can improve the welfare of the community, both in the health, education, economy (increasing income and purchasing power), ownership of assets, infrastructure, skills training and the ease of getting credit. The South Sulawesi Provincial Government has also set a target in the 2013-2018 Regional Medium Term Development Plan (RPJMD) to improve overall welfare and quality of life, namely; (i) education including number of literacy, average length of schooling, education rankings with education and scholarship facilities, (ii) health, among others health services, increasing life expectancy, (iii) assets, namely providing free assistance or subsidies in provision production / business tools, (iv) building and improving infrastructure, (v) providing soft credit and (vi) skills training, but in the RPJMD it does not have a specific target and focus on poor fishermen.

According to *Kusnadi* (2001), *Satria* (2001) and *Yustika* (2003) that fishermen are communities that have social economic classes below compared to farmers, ranchers, field workers, factory workers, and informal workers. Therefore, the *JPS* program is important for poor fishermen, among others; (i) improve social life such as education services, education levels, school enrollment rates, literacy, the average length of schooling, children's nutrition, cheap fishing houses, home improvement, and providing skills training, (ii) economics such as financial assistance and not finance, soft credit, subsidized agricultural / fishery equipment, food and tax subsidies (iii) environment such as safe living quarters, clean and healthy environment, easy access to education and health services, empowering people and others (Suharto, 2010) The importance of the JPS program is because theoretically and statistical evidence does support the quality of life. (Ravallion, 2003) Many studies find benefits to the community from the JPS program (Devereus, 2002; Smith and Subbarao, 2003; Roosgandha and Darwis, 2003; Sumarto et al. , 2005; Pradhan et al., 2013; Shahnewaz and Tareq, 2013; Rozita and Ummu, 2014).

C.2. The Challenge of Improving the Quality of Life

Indonesia as a developing country and every year provides a *JPS* budget to improve the quality of life of the community. Including the province of South Sulawesi, the challenges faced include:

1. Data Aspects Not Complete

Data collection of recipients of the Social Safety Net (JPS) program run by the National Team for the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction (TNP2K) in collaboration with the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) and the Ministries involved in JPS. The TNP2K Agency has determined the recipients of the JPS program through Data Collection of Social Protection Programs (PPLS) in 2011. Recipients of the JPS program with PPLS data in 2011 were less successful because of the fact that many did not receive the JPS program among coastal poor fishermen in Makassar City, South Sulawesi (Asang, 2012) Aspects of data that are not updated occur in all provinces in Indonesia, this is because according to the study Hastuti et al. (2012) that the data used through PPLS in 2011 is too centralistic and lacking in local socio-economic or middle to lower economic characteristics is unclear so many poor families do not receive JPS programs or vice versa.

The distribution of JPS programs such as cash assistance (BLT / BLSM, PSKS), family expectation programs, poor rice subsidies, diesel subsidies, giving BPJS Health or now a healthy Indonesian card, assistance from poor students or smart Indonesian cards that were run in 2012, 2013, 2014 and 2015 is PPLS data for 2011. The socioeconomic changes in the family will likely change so that data updates should be done before the distribution is carried out to avoid mistakes. The update system is said to be effective if it is able to ensure poor and non-poor family groups simultaneously. If the poor do not become recipients of assistance, it is called an exclusion error (exclusion error) otherwise if the non-poor group accepts it is called inclusion improvement (inclusion error).

	Gorup poor/range	Group Not poor/range
Recipient Program rang	✓	X
Non- Recipients of the Program	X	✓

Source : TNP2K

Data collection of incomplete fishermen causes many fishermen who do not receive social security cards such as free health cards. Social protection cards to take cash assistance. Fishing cards to take assistance from the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries through the provincial or district/city. An example of a case of a fishing community in the Bone region, South Sulawesi, still more than 50% had not received a fishing card so that they were threatened not to get government assistance (*Lamellongnews*, 2015). Therefore, up to date data information from the family needs to be known from the beginning. Like income, assets owned, the number of heirs and age becomes important to avoid the mistakes of recipients of *JPS* programs (Smith and *Subbarao*, 2003).

2. Aspects of *JPS* Administration and Service Capacity The capacity of *JPS*

Administrative staff and services are important in the distribution of *JPS* assistance, whether or not the success of various *JPS* programs is influenced by administrative capacity (Smith and *Subbarao*, 2003). Likewise, staff capacity is still low, so many people do not understand their roles and responsibilities, including the beneficiary community. Therefore, *JPS* service providers must know the role of including giving information widely to the public and striving for complicated administrative regulations that can be cut specifically financial flows and the need for periodic audits to consider the costs and benefits of the program (Neubourg, 2002). Besides that, administrative officers also need to be given allowances to prevent corruption cases in the distribution of *JPS* assistance, including limited institutional structure and less effective forms of *JPS* (Neubourg, 2002). Examples of corruption cases for poor rice assistance in *Bantaeng*, South Sulawesi exceed 500 million rupiah or *USD* 42 thousand (*Sindonews*, 2012) or South Sulawesi social/financial assistance that is not well targeted which exceeds 8.8 billion rupiah (*Kopel*, 2012). This is a challenge for officers in carrying out social assistance programs. Therefore, the *JPS* program also needs support from the private sector and NGOs to accelerate the welfare of the community (Morduch and Sharma, 2002) and the need for community involvement, especially those who have the capacity to distribute programs so that people feel they have the program (Neubourg, 2002), including assistance from family and relatives (Pradhan, 2013).

3. Financial Aspects

The large budget for the JPS program will have an effect on large poverty alleviation (Pradhan et al., 2013). The JPS program budget in Indonesia is only 5% or 91.8 trillion / USD 7.65 billion from the 2014 State Budget (APBN) (Ministry of Finance, 2014), while the combined social assistance budget for the provincial government of Sul-Sel and Regency Government / City only USD 5, 7 million (BPS, 2013; Financial Note of South Sulawesi, 2012). This JPS program is geared more towards non-financial assistance (Sumarto et al., 2005) such as health services, education, and infrastructure.

The central and provincial governments and districts/municipalities and parliament determine the size of the JPS budget that will be given. To the community. The government and the parliament must agree in determining the JPS budget. According to Graham (2002) whether or not the government gives a budget for the JPS program is strongly influenced by; (i) the characteristics of the poor must be clear because the middle class supports appropriate and inappropriate assistance, (ii) the backward or distant regions are perceived politically the smaller the JPS is given, (iii) ethnic diversity is related to perceptions of the composition of poverty as support for the JPS program, (iv) views on the causes of poverty, support will be weak if the view of poverty is related to individual errors such as laziness or unwillingness to try.

Soft credit assistance to fishermen who are subsidized or revolving assistance, which is initially for the poor, but in practice it is unfair or biased because those who receive only middle and upper class groups such as employers, ship employers or middlemen. This is because loans require returns in accordance with the program period, so that for the smooth running of the business and the ability to repay loans, the middle and upper classes of society are more likely to get it (Yustika, 2003). This is a challenge so that government policies better understand the characteristics and behavior of poor fishermen so that subsidized assistance can be received by poor fishermen in the area. Assistance to fishermen is generally in a non-financial form such as a large size boat and is given in groups and is not equipped with skills training for management so that sustainability does not work well.

4. Infrastructure Aspects Infrastructure

Aspects are one of the challenges in running the JPS program in Indonesia as there are still 23.25% of coastal villages with no road access for vehicles (KKP, 2011), also limited basic infrastructure such as electricity, clean water, settlements that are not good (sanitation), transportation especially the islands which are still a major challenge in development in South Sulawesi (Report of the Government of South Sulawesi, 2012). Road and bridge infrastructure outside the city that is still damaged and limited internet networks, facilities and service locations such as health, education and social services are far from where residents live. Furthermore, the facilities and infrastructure in the coastal area are also more limited so that education ranks, number of dropouts, literacy and more patients from out of town are farmers / fishermen.

5. Geographic Aspects, Culture and Local Communities

Not all countries are suitable for social safety net programs (JPS) because they are also influenced by geographic factors, culture and local communities (Tabor, 2002). The geographical factor as an archipelagic country in Indonesia is a challenge in the distribution

of JPS programs in addition to high costs and natural weather is also limited to infrastructure such as transportation (land, sea, air) and ITC (information, technology, communication). A report on the results of the South Sulawesi provincial government in 2012 states that geographical / island factors are a challenge in accessing poor rice assistance, access to education and health for the community so that there are still high numbers of illiterates and dropouts and more patients in coastal / island areas.

The cultural factor of mutual cooperation among fishermen began to fade or collapse into a negative impact if those who received JPS assistance were no longer based on agreed poverty characteristics / updated data from government institutions but the general recipients who had a closeness to the village head included the involvement of village officials. In determining the criteria for recipients of the *JPS* program. Injustice in receiving *JPS* assistance has an impact on mutual cooperation activities that are no longer followed by all communities. Then the cultural factors of consumerism and difficulties in saving among fishermen. Fishermen if they get big results will be spent to buy food/furniture/gold. On the other hand, when the bad season/weather is not good, they no longer go to sea, which has an impact on financial difficulties. Generally, they sell goods at home to meet the necessities of life or are forced to pay off with relatives, installs, or employers and brokers. While the difficulties of capital or operational costs go to sea, they borrow from the masters and this burden the captured fishermen because they are sold to the skipper at a predetermined price (*Kusnadi, 2001*).

Local communities no longer see that *JPS* beneficiaries are poor families and ranges but that assistance is shared fairly among all communities, this is because the criteria of poor are not included by the local community including data on the number of poor families / local ranges not in accordance with the family quota determined by the government. These challenges indicate that there are many aspects of the implementation of the *JPS* program to improve the quality of life, especially fishing communities.

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